

digit360

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<https://mystartupchallenge.my/>

<https://t.me/mscteam360>

<https://t.me/digit360hq>

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Malaysia Startup Challenge

*Entrepreneurship as the Frontiers of
Innovation*

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Laman Teknologi

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▶ Greetings from us

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Entrepreneurship as the Frontiers of Innovation

Entrepreneurship is the process of identifying, creating, and pursuing opportunities to start and build a new business, organization, product, or services. It involves taking calculated risks, managing resources, and innovating to create value and sustainable growth.

Nowadays, many universities and educational institutions encourage students to participate and develop their own startup as the preparation after graduation.

Thus, Malaysia Startup Challenge (MSC) is an online competition focusing on tertiary students via three categories: Startup Idea, Startup Product, and Startup Innovation.

▶ What to Expect?

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Business Idea

E01

Develop and share your business idea to potential investors.

Product Enrichment

E02

Get ideas and suggestion from expert.

Business Exposure

E03

Meet and greet with fellow potential startup.

▶ Participation Fee

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Time Moves Fast. But We Still Open for Participation.

Choose your category from the following sub-category.

▶ Participation Fee

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Local Participants

STARTUP Idea

RM100

USD50

- ✓ Tertiary Students
- ✓ Leader must be a student
- ✓ Certificate to PhD
- ✓ e-Certificate Included
- ✓ Premium Medal Included
- ✓ Lecturer/Teacher as member
- ✓ Maximun of 8 members (including teacher/lecturer)

Register now

STARTUP Product

RM100

USD50

- ✓ Tertiary Students
- ✓ Leader must be a student
- ✓ Certificate ti PhD
- ✓ e-Certificate Included
- ✓ Premium Medal Included
- ✓ Lecturer/Teacher as member
- ✓ Maximun of 8 members (including teacher/lecturer)

Register Now

STARTUP Innovation

RM100

USD50

- ✓ Tertiary Students
- ✓ Leader must be a student
- ✓ Certificate to PhD
- ✓ e-Certificate Included
- ✓ Premium Medal Included
- ✓ Lecturer/Teacher as member
- ✓ Maximun of 8 members (including teacher/lecturer)

Register Now

Manual Payment

1. All payment is processed automatically via ToyyibPay once your have register your project.
2. However, if you need to pay using Bank Transfer/ Local Order/ Cheque, you may contact us at: contact.digit360@gmail.com
3. All payment is non-refundable. Failure to submit your project within the stipulated deadline will void your participation.

▶ Startup Idea

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Focus on **business idea** or conception of a successful startup, product, or services.

1. Open to Tertiary Student from local or international educational institution.
2. Maximum of 8 members including advisor(s).
3. Participant do not need to produce a product or service – just a business idea.
4. Marks will be given based on the following criteria:
 - Problem Statement
 - Market Potential
 - Impact
 - Realistic of Ideation
 - Coverage
 - Financial Feasibility
 - Technical Feasibility
 - Product/service Mockup

▶ Startup Product

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Focus on **tangible or intangible business** product, or services.

1. Open to Tertiary Student from local or international educational institution.
2. Maximum of 8 members including advisor(s).
3. Participant needs to produce/show a product or service that currently available.
4. Marks will be given based on the following criteria:
 - Problem Statement
 - Market Potential
 - Impact
 - Realistic of Ideation
 - Coverage
 - Budgeting
 - Technical Feasibility
 - Product/service Explanation
 - Business expansion plan

▶ Startup Innovation

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Focus on **creation** or **modification of existing business** product, services or concepts.

1. Open to Tertiary Student from local or international educational institution.
2. Maximum of 8 members including advisor(s).
3. Participant need to shows the improvement of the business process, product or services that warrant for further exploration.
4. Marks will be given based on the following criteria:
 - Problem Statement
 - Commercial Potential
 - Impact to individual, society, or community
 - Realistic of Ideation
 - Completeness of Innovation
 - Innovation/Product/service Explanation

▶ MSC Poster

Malaysia Startup Challenge

The poster features a dark blue background with a grid pattern on the right side. At the top, there are logos for Laman Teknologi, DIGIT360 (Driving Innovation Forwards), DIGIT, and WORLD ALERTS (World Conference Alerts). The year '2024' is displayed in large red numbers in the top right corner. The main title 'Malaysia Startup Challenge' is written in large, bold, pink letters. To the right of the title is a large, 3D golden star trophy. Below the title, a quote reads: "Entrepreneurship Leading the Way for innovative Breakthroughs!". Underneath the quote is a checklist with three items: 'STARTUP IDEA', 'STARTUP PRODUCT', and 'STARTUP INNOVATION', each preceded by a checkmark. To the left of the checklist is an illustration of a globe with several stylized human figures standing in front of it, surrounded by glowing purple and pink energy lines. The text 'MSC2024' is prominently displayed in large white letters. Below this, the 'Registration Period' is listed as '1 December 2023 - 31 March 2024'. At the bottom, there are two lines of text: 'For More Information → https://mystartupchallenge.my' and 'Registration → https://registro/mystartupchallenge.my'.

Laman Teknologi DIGIT360 DRIVING INNOVATION FORWARDS DIGIT WORLD ALERTS WORLD CONFERENCE ALERTS

2024

Malaysia Startup Challenge

"Entrepreneurship Leading the Way for innovative Breakthroughs!"

- ✓ STARTUP IDEA
- ✓ STARTUP PRODUCT
- ✓ STARTUP INNOVATION

MSC2024

Registration Period
1 December 2023 - 31 March 2024

For More Information →
<https://mystartupchallenge.my>

Registration →
<https://registro/mystartupchallenge.my>

MSC Poster

Malaysia Startup Challenge

DIGITALLY ORGANIZED BY:
Laman Teknologi DIGIT360
DIGIT VO WORLD ALERTS

1 December 2023 - 31 March 2024

MALAYSIA **STARTUP** CHALLENGE

Entrepreneurship Leading the Way for innovative Breakthroughs!

STARTUP IDEA

Focus on a business idea or conception of a successful startup, product or services.

STARTUP PRODUCT

Focus on a tangible or intangible business product or services.

STARTUP INNOVATION

Focus on creation or modification of existing business product, services, or concept.

Web: <https://mystartupchallenge.my> | Registration: <https://registro/mystartupchallenge.my/>

▶ MSC Poster

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Online

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Entrepreneurship Leading the Way for innovative Breakthroughs!"

Enroll NOW!

Startup Idea	Startup Product	Startup Innovation
RM100 <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Idea• Tertiary students• 8 members including mentor	RM100 <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Product/Service• Tertiary students• 8 members including mentor	RM100 <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Innovation• Tertiary students• 8 members including mentor

Website: <https://mystartupchallenge.my> **Deadline:** 31s March 2024

▶ How to Register

Malaysia Startup Challenge

▶ Rules and Regulation

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Maximum of 8 members per project including teacher/lecturer

Video duration is 6 minutes to 10 minutes

Upload video to YouTube -set permission to PUBLIC or UNLISTED

You may submit additional evidence such as Business Model Canvas, Mockup Product, Testimony, etc via Google Drive. Please set permission to 'Anyone Can View'

The idea, product, or services must be original - plagiarism may lead to serious consequences

All results is non-negotiable

All projects must be lead by an active STUDENTS! Failure to comply may led to disqualification

You should apply for copyright or patent to protect your intelectual property

All payment is non-refundable

▶ Important Date

Malaysia Startup Challenge

▶ Medal

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Awarding Percentage

- 30% Gold
- 30% Silver
- 40% Bronze

** Based on jury decision, originality of innovation and other rules and/or regulation.

** All decision is final. No appeal will be entertained.

1 Unit of Medal is given for each project

Additional medal is available for purchase at RM50/medal

▶ Award

Malaysia Startup Challenge

Special Awards

- 1 x Malaysia Startup Challenge Champion
- 3 x Diamond Awards
- Top 5 Awards
- Most Innovative Idea
- Most Innovative Product
- Most Innovative Innovation

** Based on jury decision, originality of innovation and other rules and/or regulation.

** All decision is final. No appeal will be entertained.

